

N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-Cysteinato Silver(I) as a Complexing Ligand for Cu(II)*

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N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(COOH)CH_2SH$, (HSLH₂) reacts with Ag(I) at very low pH values (pH=2.5~3) to form a 1:1 complex, AgSLH, through deprotonation of its thiol (-SH) group. The complex, N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato silver (I), AgSLH₂, having -COOH and -SO₂NH- groups acted as a bidentate ligand and formed a deep-blue solution with Cu(II) at pH values 12-13. pH-Metric titration of the blue solution with HClO₄ indicated the presence of a heterometallic 2Ag(I) : Cu(II) complex containing co-ordinated water molecules. The equilibrium constant (K') of the formation of AgSLH₂, its two successive acid dissociation constants (k_{COOH} and k_{NH}) and three successive acid dissociation constants

(k'_{NH} , k''_{NH} and k'_{H_2O}) of the heterometallic 2Ag(I) : Cu(II) complex have been determined pH-metrically following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti in 50% (v/v) water dioxan medium at 29 ± 0.5° maintaining a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.50$ (NaClO₄).

The values of log K', pK_{COOH} , pK_{NH} ; pK'_{NH} , pK''_{NH} and pK'_{H_2O} have been found to be 0.26, 5.20, 11.57; 4.20, 5.50 and 11.62 respectively. The stability constant (K) of the complex ion, AgSLH⁻ has been calculated from the relation: $K = K' \cdot k_{COOH} / k_{COOH}^* \cdot k_{SH}^*$ where k_{COOH}^* and k_{SH}^* are the two successive acid dissociation constants of the ligand HSLH₂^{1a, 1b} under identical conditions and log K value has been found to be 10.65.

A study of the interactions of metal ions of different classes with the ligand N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(COOH)CH_2SH$ (NBSC or HSLH₂), having suitably placed hard (-COOH), borderline (-SO₂NH-) and soft (-SH) coordinating groups may provide valuable information about the specificities of metal binding sites in proteins which have these types of functions in their primary structures. The ligand NBSC used all its three donor sites in complexing borderline metal ions e.g., Zn(II), Cd(II)^{1a, 1b} but used only its -SO₂NH- and -SH functions in complexing soft metal ions Hg(II)^{1c} and Co(II) and Ni(II)². The present communication describes a pH-metric study of the interaction of a softer metal ion Ag(I) with the ligand NBSC and the ligand action of the complex N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato silver(I), AgSLH₂ formed thereby on Cu(II) to produce a heterometallic 2Ag : Cu(II) complex in 50% (v/v) water-dioxan medium having constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.50 M$ (NaClO₄) at 29 ± 0.5°.

Experimental

Materials : The ligand HSLH₂ was prepared and purified by the procedure described earlier^{1c, 2}. The complex N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato silver(I), AgSLH₂ was obtained as a white solid by mixing equimolar quantities of the ligand HSLH₂ and Ag(I) in 1 : 1 aqueous dioxan at pH 2.~3.0.

It was washed with water, dried and analysed. Found : Ag 29.31 ; N, 3.74 ; Calcd. Ag, 29.35 ; N, 3.80%. The sodium salt, AgSLHNa was prepared by dissolving AgSLH₂ (0.01 mole) in a concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide (0.01 mole) and concentrating the mixture in a vacuum desiccator to a small volume and adding absolute alcohol. AgSLHNa separated as a white solid. It was washed with ice cold water and finally with rectified spirit, dried and analysed. Found : Na, 5.94 ; Ag, 27.62 ; N, 3.54 ; Calcd. Na, 5.90 ; Ag, 27.67 ; N, 3.59%. Exposure to light was avoided as far as practicable. Infrared spectra of HSLH₂, AgSLH₂ and AgSLHNa were recorded in KBr phase and it was found that the $\nu(S-H)$ at 2597 cm⁻¹ (HSLH₂) was absent in the spectra of both the silver complexes, AgSLH₂ and AgSLHNa. The characteristic band for -COOH group at 1730-1735 cm⁻¹ (HSLH₂) was retained in the spectra of the complex AgSLH₂, but it was absent in the spectra of the sodium salt, AgSLHNa, in which two new bands, one at 1610 cm⁻¹ and the other at 1410 cm⁻¹, characteristics of $\nu_{sym}(COO^-)$ and $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ respectively appeared. The bands due to -SO₂N< group at 1330-1340 cm⁻¹ and 1165 cm⁻¹ were present in all the three compounds, HSLH₂, AgSLH₂ and AgSLHNa. It was, therefore, concluded that the complex AgSLH₂ was formed by deprotonation of the thiol group of the ligand and in forming the sodium salt, AgSLHNa the -COOH group of AgSLH₂ was deprotonated.

Apparatus: pH measurements were made with a Cambridge pH-Meter (Portable Type) having a glass electrode of 1-13 pH range and a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an Agar-2M NaNO₃ bridge. The meter was calibrated using standard 0.01M HClO₄ solution, phthalate buffer and borate buffer solutions with appropriate temperature corrections.

Procedure: The following solutions were prepared for the pH-metric study:

- (1) 0.005(M) HClO₄
- (2) 0.005(M) HClO₄ + 0.001(M) HSLH₂
- (2a) 0.005(M) HClO₄ + 0.002(M) HSLH₂
- (3) 0.005(M) HClO₄ + 0.001(M) HSLH₂ + 0.001(M) AgClO₄
- (4) 0.005(M) HClO₄ + 0.002(M) HSLH₂ + 0.002(M) AgClO₄
- (5) 0.0005(M) AgSLHNa
- (6) 0.00125(M) AgSLHNa
- (7) 0.002(M) NaOH
- (8) 0.002(M) NaOH + 0.001(M) HSLH₂ + 0.001(M) AgClO₄ + 0.003(M) NaOH
- (9) 0.002(M) NaOH + 0.001(M) HSLH₂ + 0.001(M) AgClO₄ + 0.0005(M) Cu(ClO₄)₂ + 0.003(M) NaOH

In each case the total volume was made up to 50 ml maintaining the 1 : 1 ratio of dioxan to water. All the solutions were shaken well and allowed to attain equilibrium at the required temperature. Any contractions in volume were made up with 1 : 1 dioxan-water mixture. The mixture numbers (1), (2), (3) and (4) were titrated with a standard 0.051(M) NaOH in 1 : 1 dioxan-water and titrations of mixture numbers (7), (8) and (9) were made with a standard 0.025(M) HClO₄ in the same solvent. Mixture (5) was titrated with a standard 0.005(M) HClO₄ and mixture (6) with a 0.01282(M) NaOH both in 1 : 1 dioxan-water. Appropriate amounts of NaClO₄ were added to maintain the ionic strength constant ($\mu=0.50$). The titration curves, pH (volume of titrant) were plotted (Fig. 1).

Results and Discussion

(I) Interaction of Ag(I) with HSLH₂:

A white solid compound of composition AgSLH₂ was precipitated at the very early stage (pH 2.5-3.0) of the titration of solution numbers (3) and (4). Infrared study (*Loc. cit.*) indicated the formation of AgSLH₂ through deprotonation of the thiol

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves: Initial volume=50 ml; 1 : 1 water-dioxan, $\mu=0.50M$ (NaClO₄).

- Curve 1: 0.005(M) HClO₄
 Curve 2: 0.005(M) HClO₄ + 0.001(M) HSLH₂
 Curve 3: 0.005(M) HClO₄ + 0.001(M) HSLH₂ + 0.001(M) AgClO₄
 Curve 4: 0.005(M) HClO₄ + 0.002(M) HSLH₂ + 0.002(M) AgClO₄
 Titrant: 0.0510(M) NaOH
 Curve 5: 0.0005(M) AgSLHNa, Titrant: 0.005(M) HClO₄
 Curve 6: 0.00125(M) AgSLHNa, Titrant: 0.01282(M) NaOH
 Curve 7: 0.002(M) NaOH
 Curve 8: 0.002(M) NaOH + 0.001(M) HSLH₂ + 0.001(M) AgClO₄ + 0.003(M) NaOH
 Curve 9: 0.002(M) NaOH + 0.001(M) HSLH₂ + 0.001(M) AgClO₄ + 0.0005(M) Cu(ClO₄)₂ + 0.003(M) NaOH
 Titrant: 0.025(M) HClO₄

(-SH) group of the ligand by Ag(I). Thus, the initial step in the reaction of Ag(I) with the ligand, HSLH₂ may be represented by (1)

for which, K' is the equilibrium constant. The average number (\bar{n}_h) of protons released due to this reaction was expressed by the relation (2):

$$\bar{n}_h = \frac{([\text{AgSLH}_2]/T_{\text{Ag}})}{\left(\frac{K'}{[\text{H}^+]} [\text{HSLH}_2]\right) / \left(1 + \frac{K'}{[\text{H}^+]} [\text{HSLH}_2]\right)} \quad \dots (2)$$

where the terms within the brackets [] represent the equilibrium concentrations of the respective species and T_{Ag} is the total concentration of silver ions. The values of \bar{n}_h and [HSLH₂] were calculated from the pH titration curves 1 and 3 (Fig. 1) following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁴. The log K' value was found out from the graphical solution of the relation (3) (Curve a, Fig. 3):

$$(pHSLH_2 - pH) = \log(1 - \bar{n}_h) / \bar{n}_h + \log K' \quad \dots (3)$$

and also by curve fitting method using the plot of \bar{n}_h against $(pHSLH_2 - pH)$ [Curve (a), Fig. 2].

Fig. 2. (a) \bar{n}_h ($pHSLH_2 - pH$) plot for the reaction (1) (b) \bar{n}_h (pH) plot for $AgSLH_2$ (c) \bar{n}_h (pH) plot for heterometallic $2Ag(I) : Cu(II)$ complex in the pH range from 10.0 to 12.0 and (d) same as in (c) in the pH range from 4.0 to 10.0.

(II) Successive Acid Dissociation of the Complex N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-Cysteinato Silver(I), $AgSLH_2$:

The complex $AgSLH_2$ behaved as a dibasic acid releasing two protons in succession according to :

where k_{COOH} and k_{NH} are the two successive acid dissociation constants. Infrared study (*Loc. cit.*) on $AgSLH_2$ and $AgSLHNa$ suggests that the first step acid dissociation involves the deprotonation of the carboxyl group.

The average number of protons (\bar{n}_H) bound to the complex ion $AgSL^{2-}$ were calculated by following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁴ using the pH titration curves of solutions (7) and (8) [Curves 7 and 8, Fig. 1] and also using the relation :

$$\bar{n}_H = 1 + (E + [OH^-] - [H^+]) / T_{AgSLHNa} \quad \dots (6)$$

for the titration of solution (5) i.e., of $AgSLHNa$ with standard $HClO_4$ [Curve 5, Fig. 1] and from the relation :

$$\bar{n}_H = 1 - (P + [H^+] - [OH^-]) / T_{AgSLHNa} \quad \dots (7)$$

for the titration of solution (6) of $AgSLHNa$ with standard $NaOH$ (Curve 6, Fig. 1), where, $T_{AgSLHNa}$ is the total concentration of $AgSLHNa$, E and P are the analytical concentrations and $[H^+]$ and $[OH^-]$ are the equilibrium concentrations of acid and alkali respectively. The values of $[H^+]$ and $[OH^-]$ were obtained from the plots $pH(-\log [H^+])$ and $pH(-\log [OH^-])$ of the titration of solution (1) (Curve 1, Fig. 1). The plot \bar{n}_H (pH), [Curve (b), Fig. 2] shows that there is an appreciable difference of pH between the two ionisation steps (4) and (5) and that they may be considered independent of one another and consequently the value of pK_{NH} was obtained from graphical solution [Curve (b), Fig. 3] of the relation (8) :

$$pH = \log(1 - \bar{n}_H) / \bar{n}_H + pK_{NH} \quad \dots (8)$$

using the \bar{n}_H (pH) data in the region $0.2 < \bar{n}_H < 0.8$.

Fig. 3. Linear plots for the evolution of : (a) $\log K'$, (b) pK_{NH} of $AgSLH_2$ (c) pK'_{OH_2} and (d) pK''_{NH} and pK'''_{NH} of the heterometallic $2Ag(I) : Cu(II)$ complex.

Both pK_{COOH} and pK_{NH} values were obtained by curve fitting method using the \bar{n}_H (pH) plot, [Curve (b), Fig. 2]. \bar{n}_H values greater than 1.1 could not be obtained due to the commencement of precipitation of $AgSLH_2$ nearly at $pH \approx 6$. The pK value of the $-COOH$ group of the ligand, $HSLH_2$ (i.e., pK_{COOH}) under identical condition^{1a} was 4.44 while that of the silver compound, $AgSLH_2$ has been found to be 5.20. The weakening of the carboxylate acidity is probably due to some sort of electron releasing inductive effect arising from the delocalisation of electrons from $Ag(I)$ to the d_π orbitals of thiol sulphur atom.

The stability constant (K) of the complex ion $AgSLH^-$ have been calculated using the relation

$$K = \frac{(AgSLH^-)}{(Ag^+)(SLH^{2-})} = \frac{K' k_{COOH}}{k_{COOH} k_{SH}} \quad \dots (9)$$

(III) Protonation of the Heterometallic 2Ag(I) : Cu(II) Complex :

The deep blue solution containing Cu(II) : Ag(I) : HSLH₂ : NaOH :: 1 : 2 : 2 : 6 together with some known amount (P) of NaOH had a pH value lower than that of a solution (7) containing the same amount (P) of alkali under identical condition (curves 7 and 9, Fig. 1). This has been attributed to the deprotonation of a solvent water molecule on co-ordination to either of the metal ion Cu²⁺ or Ag⁺, to be decided by detailed structural study on isolation. The deep blue solution consumed one equivalent of mineral acid per mole of Cu(II) in the pH range 12.5~10.0 and then two equivalents in the pH range 7 to 4. The titration could not be completed due to the commencement of precipitation at lower pH values ≈4.0. The enhancement of acidity of the -SO₂NH- group on co-ordination to metal ions leading to its deprotonation at lower pH values (4-8) have been observed in a number of cases^{1a, 1b, 1c, 2, 6}. In the present case such deprotonation of -SO₂NH- group has been assumed to take place on coordination of this group of AgSLH⁻ to Cu(II) through the formation of a heterometallic 2Ag(I) : Cu(II) complex of the type (AgSL) Cu (LSAg), and consequently two equivalents of mineral acids were consumed in the pH range from 7 to 4 with the formation of a species of the type (AgSLH) Cu(HLSAg). The one equivalent of acid that was consumed at higher pH values (12.5-10.0) was assumed to be taken up by a deprotonated water molecule co-ordinated to either of the metal ions Cu(II) or Ag(I). Thus the prevailing species in solution (9) before the addition of any mineral acid titrant has been suggested to be a species of the type [(AgSL)-Cu(LSAg)(OH)], which consumed three equivalents of acid in a stepwise manner as shown below :

where k'''_{NH} , k''_{NH} and k'_{OH_2} are the successive acid dissociation constants of the heterometallic 2Ag(I) : Cu(II) complex.

Average number of protons (\bar{n}'_h) bound to the heterometallic 2Ag(I) : Cu(II) complex ion [(AgSL)-Cu(LSAg)(OH)]³⁻ was expressed by the relation (13) :

$$\bar{n}'_h = \frac{3[(AgSLH)Cu(HLSAg)(OH_2)] + 2[(AgSLH)Cu(LSAg)(OH_2)]^{1-} + [(AgSL)Cu(LSAg)(OH_2)]^{2-}}{[(AgSLH)Cu(HLSAg)(OH_2)] + [(AgSLH)Cu(LSAg)(OH_2)]^{1-} + [(AgSL)Cu(LSAg)(OH_2)]^{2-} + [(AgSL)Cu(LSAg)(OH)]^{3-}} \quad \dots (13)$$

The \bar{n}'_h values were calculated following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁴ using pH titration curves of solutions 7 and 9 (Curves 7 and 9, Fig. 1). The \bar{n}'_h (pH) plots [Curve (c) and (d), Fig. 2] show that the first step protonation (10) is independent of the second step (11) while the second step and third step (12) are overlapping. The pk'_{OH_2} value was obtained by curve fitting method using the curve (c), Fig. 2, and also by graphical solution [Curve (d), Fig. 3] of the relation (14) :

$$pH = \log (1 - \bar{n}'_h) / \bar{n}'_h + pk'_{OH_2} \quad \dots (14)$$

which can be deduced from the relation (13) assuming the concentrations of the species [(AgSLH)-Cu(HLSAg)(OH₂)] and [(AgSLH)Cu(LSAg)(OH₂)]¹⁻ negligibly small in comparison to those of the species [(AgSL)Cu(LSAg)(OH₂)]²⁻ and [(AgSL)Cu(LSAg)(OH)]³⁻ in the pH range 10.0-12.5. The values of k'_{NH} and k''_{NH} were obtained from the linear plot of the relation (15) :

$$\left(\frac{\bar{n}'_h - 1}{3 - \bar{n}'_h} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]^2} = \frac{1}{k'_{NH}} \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]} \cdot \left(\frac{2 - \bar{n}'_h}{3 - \bar{n}'_h} \right) + \frac{1}{k''_{NH}k'_{NH}} \quad \dots (15)$$

which can be deduced from the relation (13) assuming the concentration of [(AgSL)Cu(LSAg)(OH)]³⁻ ion negligible in comparison to those of the species [(AgSLH)Cu(HLSAg)(OH₂)], [(AgSLH)Cu(LSAg)(OH₂)]¹⁻ and [(AgSL)Cu(LSAg)(OH₂)]²⁻ in the pH range 9.0-4.0 and using the equilibrium constants of the reactions (11) and (12).

The values of log K' ; pk_{COOH} , pk_{NH} ; log K ; pk'''_{NH} , pk''_{NH} and pk'_{OH_2} are stated in Table 1. Standard deviations (σ) were calculated in the usual

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF pH-METRIC STUDY OF THE REACTION OF Ag(I) WITH NBSO₂ IN THE PRESENCE AND IN THE ABSENCE OF Cu(II), IN 50% (v/v) WATER-DIOXAN MEDIUM, $\mu = 0.50M(NaClO_4)$ AND AT $29 \pm 0.5^\circ$

pk'_{COOH}	pk''_{SH}	log K'	pk_{COOH}	pk_{NH}	log K	pk'''_{NH}	pk''_{NH}	pk'_{OH_2}
4.44	11.15	0.26	5.20	11.57	10.65	4.20	5.50	11.62

manner^{4a} and have been found to be in the range $\pm 0.010 - \pm 0.03$. Calculated \bar{n} values required for this purpose were obtained on solving suitable forms of the relation :

$$\bar{n} = \left(\sum_1^n \frac{n[H^+]^n}{\bar{n}k_n} \right) / \left(1 + \sum_1^n \frac{[H^+]^n}{\bar{n}k_n} \right) \quad \dots (16)$$

using the values of the constants determined and experimental pH values. Smaller values of σ in all the cases justify the validity of the assumptions made.

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